

A Master of Science project submitted to the
Graduate Program at the Institute of Physics, University of Sao Paulo

Title: Assessing wildfire radiative power and pollution in the Amazon Basin

Candidate: Mr. Thiago Ferreira da Nobrega

Advisor: Prof. Dr. Alexandre L. Correia

Institution: Institute of Physics, University of Sao Paulo

Date: 2021-12-20

Document DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5748358>

Abstract

Deforestation in the Amazon is currently the most significant source of greenhouse gas emissions in Brazil. Anthropogenic wildfires are routinely used in the region as a land-clearing tool for the economic exploitation of forest goods and land. Tracking the temporal evolution of wildfire emitted radiant power enables the estimation of the amount of gas and smoke emitted during combustion processes. This project will combine orbital retrievals of Amazon wildfire radiative power, area, and temperature with fire emission inventories to investigate gas and particle emission in case studies. Time series at high temporal resolution (10-15 minutes) and 2 km nominal spatial resolution will be used to study wildfire dynamics according to biome type, and season of the year. By integrating the radiative power over time, the total emitted energy will be calculated. Gas and particulate matter emission estimates will be derived from the total emitted energy and from the instantaneous radiative power, depending on requirements set by different fire emission inventories. The results will be compared to independent ground and space-borne derived retrievals, and with the published literature. The goals that will be sought by this project will bring new insights about emissions due to biomass burning events in the Amazon, potentially helping to develop monitoring and conservation strategies for the emission of greenhouse gases and smoke in the region.

1. Introduction

The Amazon Basin is one of Earth's most complex environments and plays a fundamental role in regulating the climate. From atmospheric convection, energy transport, hydrology, and the water cycle, to fauna and flora ecosystem services, and biogeochemical cycles (Strand et al., 2018), with nonlinear physicochemical relations between all these intertwined parts. However, due to anthropic expansion, it is estimated that about 23% of the original forest has been destroyed or damaged, triggering concerns that we are approaching a climatic tipping point (Brando et al., 2020; Lovejoy and Nobre, 2019). The southern and eastern sections of the Amazon Basin are especially subject to significant deforestation. Fire is the preferred land-clearing method, causing severe pollution events concentrated in about three months every year, typically from August to October (Ten Hoeve et al., 2012).

Deforestation in the Amazon is the most important factor contributing to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and pollution in Brazil. It is estimated that, in 2020, about 46% of the total 2.16×10^9 ton CO₂-equivalent gross Brazilian GHG emissions were due to deforestation¹. Pollution from biomass burning

¹ https://www.oc.eco.br/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/OC_03_relatorio_2021_FINAL.pdf accessed 2021-12-01 15:00 UTC.

affects millions of people in the Amazon and causes damage to human lung cells (de Oliveira Alves et al., 2017). Smoke aerosol particles are also transported downwind and spread out to occupy large fractions of the South American continent (Martins et al., 2018). These particles induce micro and macrophysical changes in cloud properties (Correia et al., 2021) and may change precipitation patterns.

Understanding wildfire dynamics is the key element that interconnects the characterization of GHG and aerosol emissions in the Amazon. Depending on the type of vegetation substrate, wildfires will progress differently, and consequently, the rates of gaseous and particulate emissions will vary. While in situ field campaigns can establish “ground truth” as a definite reference, orbital sensors are an invaluable tool to assess wildfire temporal evolution over large spatial domains. National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) operates Terra and Aqua satellites, for which the Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) sensor retrieves the occurrence and other physical parameters of fire spots twice daily, in daytime and nighttime orbits. Hence, by combining both satellites it is possible to characterize wildfire properties four times a day. National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) and NASA have been operating the Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellites (GOES) for decades. The geostationary platform allows retrieving wildfire properties several times a day, which is essential for understanding fire temporal evolution, although at coarser spatial resolution compared to polar satellites.

In Brazil, the National Institute for Space Research (INPE) uses a combination of ten polar and geostationary satellites to generate multiple time series of detected fire spots. Detections by MODIS Aqua daytime orbit are currently considered the reference for long-term assessments. Figure 1 shows INPE’s curated historical yearly time series of wildfire hotspots in the Brazilian Legal Amazon Basin. After peaking in 2004, a combination of change in governance and favorable international economical conditions helped curb the anthropic expansion against forested areas. This led to a marked reduction in fire use and forest degradation, leading some to ponder on a possible end of deforestation in the Amazon (Nepstad et al., 2009). In 2005, 2007, and 2010 pronounced droughts caused spikes in the number of fires. These strong anomalies may be the result of a carbon feedback loop, in which the currently elevated anthropic CO₂ concentrations favor the increased occurrence of wildfires (Brando et al., 2020).

Figure 1. Historical time series of fire pixel detection in Brazilian Amazon Basin.
Source: National Institute for Space Research² (INPE).

² https://queimadas.dgi.inpe.br/queimadas/porta-static/estatisticas_estados accessed 2021-12-01 15:00 UTC.

Despite their uncontested usefulness, satellite sensors may incur observational constraints that need to be addressed when assessing wildfire physical properties. For instance, polar satellites in low altitude orbits can perform measurements with a high spatial resolution (e.g. tens to hundreds of meters), but have low return rates, in general with one or two daily observations per satellite, as discussed above. Specifically for MODIS, limitations to the instrument lateral swath prevent overlaps between consecutive overpasses near the equator, causing data gaps in this region of the planet. Under these observational limitations, the occurrence of clouds also compounds to hinder the retrieval of wildfire counts, by obscuring the sensor line of sight. This is especially relevant over the Amazon, with yearlong ubiquitous convective cloud formation conditions. Sensors aboard geostationary satellites, on the other hand, can generate many observations every day, at coarser spatial resolutions when compared to polar satellites. For this reason, geostationary sensors are usually less capable of detecting smaller, more frequent fire spots. Clouds also hamper geostationary wildfire retrievals, but since these sensors can have multiple daily observation opportunities, in principle fire spots detection can be ameliorated based on spatial-temporal correlation patterns.

Besides detecting the occurrence of wildfire hotspots, other physical parameters are important to characterize fire dynamics and associated gaseous emissions. The Fire Radiative Power (FRP) can be used to follow the instantaneous radiative emission intensity in wildfires (Roberts et al., 2005; Wooster et al., 2005). The formal FRP definition is discussed in the next section. The main idea behind the FRP concept is to measure the radiance emitted by the wildfire surface, using a wavelength for which there is enough contrast with the surrounding non-fire background. The chosen wavelength must also be relatively free from atmospheric absorption and emission along the optical path between target and sensor. This technique can be used in situ or by orbital sensors (Wooster et al., 2005).

Orbital FRP retrievals are subject to artifacts the more distinct the pixel spatial resolution is from the observed wildfire size scale. Coarse pixel retrievals will often miss smaller fires since their emitted power may not cross a specific threshold for detection. Finer resolution pixels may saturate if the sensor radiometric bit depth is not, or cannot be built with enough dynamic range to cover measuring conditions typical of colder, i.e. smoldering, and hotter flaming fires. Considering just the measured FRP by itself, the retrieval at one given pixel may be physically due to a relatively small fire at high temperature, or a large burning area at lower temperatures. For this reason, it is critical to have ancillary information retrieved in parallel at the subpixel level, to help contextualize the fire area and its temperature. This can be done by employing multiwavelength detectors, with different spatial resolutions for each channel. Another possible issue that needs to be considered is partial radiative absorption and emission by atmospheric gases, in the sensor line of sight, when determining the fire temperature. While temperature retrievals are always performed at atmospheric window wavelength ranges, there is residual absorption that may become relevant in the case of copious amounts of emitted water vapor³, especially in large wildfires.

³ A. Setzer, personal communication, 2021.

1.1 FRP retrieval physical basis

The orbital detection of active wildfires FRP is based on Planck's radiation law. The infrared radiation emitted by a perfect blackbody is given by:

$$B_{\lambda}(\lambda, T) = \frac{2hc^2}{\lambda^5 \left(\exp\left(\frac{hc}{\lambda k_B T}\right) - 1 \right)} \quad (1)$$

where λ is the wavelength, T is the temperature, h is Planck's constant, c is the speed of light, and k_B is the Boltzmann constant. Figure 2, extracted from Wooster et al. (2021), shows a simulation of B_{λ} according to wavelength and temperature. At shorter 3-4 μm wavelengths the contrast in emitted radiation for different T is noticeably stronger than at longer 10-11 μm .

Figure 2. Emitted spectral radiance for blackbody temperatures of 300, 600, and 1000 K (Wooster et al., 2021).

Wooster et al. (2003) showed that, empirically, the orbitally measured radiance, L_{λ} , can be approximately parameterized by a function of the temperature to the fourth power, such that:

$$L_{\lambda} = \epsilon_{\lambda} B_{\lambda}(\lambda, T) \approx \alpha \epsilon_{\lambda} T^4 \rightarrow T^4 \approx \frac{L_{\lambda}}{\alpha \epsilon_{\lambda}} \quad (2)$$

where ϵ_{λ} is the emissivity at the wavelength λ , α is a proportionality constant, and the approximation is only valid for λ in the 3-4 μm range and $500 < T < 1500$ K. α is derived based on the filter function for the specific sensor used in the measurements. The approximation in Eq. (2) is fortunate since it can be compared to Stefan-Boltzmann law to allow retrieving the FRP:

$$\text{FRP} = A \epsilon \sigma T^4 \approx A \frac{\epsilon \sigma}{\alpha \epsilon_{\lambda}} L_{\lambda} \quad (3)$$

where A is the fire area, ϵ is the emissivity across all wavelengths, and σ is the Stefan-Boltzmann constant. In practice, the fire emissivity at λ is considered equivalent to ϵ (gray body approximation) and these terms cancel out (Wooster et al., 2003). This method has the numerical advantage that the retrieved FRP is

linearly proportional to the product between the fire area, A , and the net radiance, L_λ , measured by the sensor. Net radiance ($L_\lambda = L_\lambda^f - L_\lambda^o$) is the difference between the radiance measured at the fire pixel, L_λ^f , and the radiance the same pixel would have under no fire conditions, L_λ^o , usually approximated by the radiance measured at nearby fire-free pixels. Notice that the parameterization described by Eq. (2) indicates the FRP retrievals may work poorly for fires with $T < 500$ K, i.e. smoldering wildfire conditions. These limitations on minimum fire temperature are therefore intrinsic to this method used to derive FRP, independent of the capabilities of the instrument sensor used.

1.2 Gaseous and particulate wildfire emissions

Estimates of gaseous and particulate emissions have been accomplished using empirical parameterizations derived from in situ measurements and instrument intercomparison efforts. Wooster et al. (2021) summarized the general approach employed in deriving emission inventories, that seek to relate wildfire physical characteristics to the emission process for several gases and particulate matter.

Firstly, the total mass of burnt material was found to be proportional to the total emitted wildfire energy (i.e. integrating FRP over time) (Wooster et al., 2021). The total emitted mass of a given species during the combustion process is then:

$$M_x = EF_x \cdot M_{burnt} \rightarrow M_x \propto EF_x \int FRP(t) dt \quad (4)$$

where M_x is the mass of the species, EF_x is the emission factor for species x , and M_{burnt} is the mass of burnt material. In practice, the proportionality constant needed to estimate M_x from Eq. (4) is contingent on biome type, specific burning conditions, such as the existence or not of understory combustion, and on the satellite sensor used in the estimate (Wooster et al., 2021). Therefore, emission inventories that are based on EF_x compilations, are specific for a given satellite imagery dataset and biome.

Instead of seeking first an estimate for M_{burnt} , another approach is to use FRP to directly derive the rate of emission for species x , R_x , in units of kg s^{-1} :

$$R_x = C_e^x \cdot FRP \quad (5)$$

where C_e^x is the emission coefficient for species x , typically in units of $10^{-6} \text{ kg J}^{-1}$, and the total emitted mass for species x can be obtained by integrating R_x over time (Wooster et al., 2021).

Several fire emission inventory databases, based on compilations of either EF_x or C_e^x , are currently available (cf. Table 2 in Wooster et al., 2021). Intercomparison studies, in general, find large deviations between inventories. In one particular study, Wooster et al. (2021) found a factor of 2 for the range of results using different inventories to estimate particulate emissions in Africa for one specific time interval. The same authors highlight that in 2014 a factor of 12 was found between inventories, therefore it appears that improvements toward convergence of estimations are being performed. These large discrepancies arise from the simplified assumptions involved in deriving these inventories. Uncertainties are due to variations amidst the set of different satellite sensor capabilities, such as temporal and spatial resolution,

radiometric bit depth, filter function wavelength range, but also due to the inherent complexity of vegetation dynamics involving plant and soil moisture, growth and senescence patterns, the occurrence of clouds and precipitation, and other factors that may vary seasonally for each biome under analysis. Such limitations need to be acknowledged and considered when interpreting emission estimates.

1.3 Scientific objectives

This plan aims to use high temporal resolution (10-15 min) orbital FRP retrievals to study wildfires in the Brazilian Amazon Basin, and discover new insights on GHG emissions from the correlation of retrieved FRP and fire emission inventories.

This project has the following specific objectives:

- a) To physically characterize individual wildfire clusters, based on detailed time series of fire temperature, area, radiative power, for different vegetation cover types, in a statistically robust fashion;
- b) To correlate wildfire characteristics with vegetation type and emission inventories, and derive GHG and aerosol emission estimates, using published emission factors or coefficients;
- c) To critically evaluate the resulting estimates, by comparing them with measurements from other instruments and the published literature.

2. Materials and methods

Since 2017 NOAA and NASA have been operating the newest geostationary satellite in the GOES series, GOES-16, stationed at the equatorial 75.2°W position. While previous GOES versions were mainly focused on weather forecasting, GOES-16 shows advanced instrumentation, data collection, and transfer capabilities that put it on par with the scientific efficiency of polar satellites. Its most important sensor is the Advanced Baseline Imager (ABI), which counts 16 spectral channels, with 2 in the visible spectrum, 4 in near-infrared, and 10 in infrared. Nominal spatial resolutions are either 0.5 km, 1 km, or 2 km depending on the channel (Schmit et al., 2018). In contrast, previous GOES imager sensors counted 4 or 5 channels, only one visible channel at 1 km spatial resolution, and 4 km or more for the remaining infrared channels. ABI operates by selecting special geographical sectors, some of which are focused on the continental United States. For this project, the relevant geographical coverage corresponds to the “full disk” mode, when the entire hemispherical field of view accessible to ABI is sampled. The sensor is also operated in specific “scan modes” that define the acquisition frequency. The default scan mode 6 produces full disk imagery every 10 minutes, while mode 3 acquires images every 15 minutes. Both modes can be used for the objectives of this plan.

The ABI fire detection and characterization product⁴ estimates FRP (in MW units), fire temperature (K), and area (m²) every 10 to 15 minutes depending on the scan mode, with a nominal pixel resolution of 2 km. In particular, notice that fire temperature and area are derived from subpixel radiance measurements

⁴ <https://www.goes-r.gov/products/baseline-fire-hot-spot.html> accessed 2021-12-01 12:00 UTC.

and reported at the 2 km resolution. This allows for better accuracy in retrieving the fraction of burnt area in a given scene. The temporal and spatial resolution for this product enables adequate characterization of fire dynamics over large parts of the Americas, but especially over the Amazon in South America, due to its proximity to the equatorial region (Xu et al., 2021).

Preliminary evaluations have been performed to compare the ABI retrieved FRP with higher spatial resolution (750 m) retrievals by the Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer Suite (VIIRS) (Li et al., 2020). VIIRS is onboard the Suomi National Polar-Orbiting Partnership satellite, with twice-daily observations of a given wildfire scene. In comparing ABI to VIIRS, Li et al. (2020) showed the GOES-16 sensor is able to replicate higher resolution results for wildfires with FRP larger than 34.5 MW. Figure 3, extracted from Li et al. (2020), indicates that smaller, or smoldering condition fires are relatively undersampled by GOES-16, taking VIIRS as reference. The instrumental comparison with VIIRS is specific for the type of imager sensor and spatial resolution used in GOES-16. Compared to GOES-13, the previous generation geostationary imager, GOES-16 outperforms the former sensor in many aspects, with smaller commission and omission errors (i.e. positive and negative misidentification of active fires), better FRP performance when dealing with single fires, or in area-averages, better reproduction of the FRP diurnal cycle, and less frequent occurrence of channel saturation (Xu et al., 2021).

Figure 3. FRP comparison between GOES-16 ABI at 2 km and VIIRS at 750 m spatial resolutions. Peak frequency indicates the minimum FRP that can be reliably retrieved by each sensor (Li et al., 2020).

The methodology proposed here starts by determining a spatial and temporal window with enough wildfire clusters to analyze, and derive robust characterizations of fire properties and emission statistics. In the southern part of the Amazon the cerrado region has diverse vegetation characteristics and is different from forest contact regions, e.g. sections where roads adjacent to the forest correlate with nearby logging

and fire usage (“fishbone” patterns). Various local biomes should be sampled and results aggregated whenever they are statistically coherent.

Preliminary GOES-16 fire product analyses need to take into account physical and operational limitations discussed previously, regarding for instance the minimum and maximum fire temperature, and the minimum FRP that can be reliably retrieved. The Data Quality Flag and the Fire Mask are diagnostic variables, available in the regular GOES-16 ABI fire product, that also help screen the data to eliminate cloudy pixels, pixels over water bodies, or close to the backscattering direction where the enhanced surface reflection prevents the detection of wildfires. Cases for which the input data was not accurate, or for which the algorithm failed are also identified. The Fire Mask diagnostic also allows the identification of regularly processed fire pixels, saturated, and cloud contaminated pixels. Identification under one of these three categories indicates the algorithm was able to detect fires, but the quality of retrieved output may vary. It is therefore possible to study how strict one needs to impose the pixel selection to establish a compromise between the remaining number of pixels after filtering, and the quality of the results. Other Fire Mask categories that may be studied are named high, moderate, and low possibility fire detection, when pixels have the potential to be defined as wildfires, but the classification is less certain.

Initial tests will determine temporal boundaries for a given wildfire cluster under analysis, and the potential impact of cloud obscuration. For instance, if an FRP time series is partially compromised with missing data due to cloud occurrence, it is necessary to study whether interpolation can be used to ameliorate the issue, and what percentual level of missing data can be inferred in this manner. Once this step is completed, the FRP time series can be integrated over time to derive the total amount of radiant energy emitted by a given wildfire cluster.

Available fire emission inventories (Wooster et al., 2021) will be scrutinized to develop a qualitative assessment of suitability for the analyses intended to represent Amazon Basin emissions. Some of the inventories rely on the number of detected wildfire pixels, the burnt area, or the total radiant energy emitted, while others directly use the retrieved FRP to estimate emissions for each species. Studying the applicability of such inventories also needs to consider different biomes, seasonal variations, precipitation occurrence, and surface properties.

The derived gas and particulate matter emission estimates can be compared to retrievals by independent instruments. For instance, sun photometers from NASA’s Aerosol Robotic Network (AERONET) (Holben et al., 1998) retrieve the aerosol optical depth, which can be used to infer the particulate matter concentration at ground level (e.g. (He et al., 2021)). Polar orbit sensors will be used to infer gaseous concentrations, e.g. by employing NASA’s Orbiting Carbon Observatory⁵ 2 and 3. In principle, these comparisons can be made, but none of these remote sensing instruments can represent “ground truth” standards, which require in situ measurements.

⁵ https://docserver.gesdisc.eosdis.nasa.gov/public/project/OCO/OCO2_L2_ATBD.V6.pdf accessed 2021-12-01 15:00 UTC.

3. Expected results and challenges to be addressed

The technical feasibility of the project is discussed next. The access to the relevant datasets to be used in this project is not subject to any foreseeable uncertainty. GOES-16 ABI fire product datasets are freely available on the internet in several web portals, such as NOAA's Comprehensive Large Array-data Stewardship System (CLASS) repository⁶. These datasets run from 2017, at the start of GOES-16 operations, to the current day. Storing and managing data files, and infrastructure challenges, in principle, are also not significant, since the main product file size is about 3.6 MB and thus can be easily manipulated. Our planned use of databases for emission inventories is restricted to case studies, and therefore we do not anticipate technical bottlenecks.

To illustrate the analytical framework proposed in the project, Figure 4 shows an example of retrieved GOES-16 ABI fire product data, for August 15th 2020, when large fires spread out over Brazilian wetlands (Libonati et al., 2020; Pivello et al., 2021). Fig. 4a shows the data quality flag, which allows distinguishing between active wildfires (red) and background pixels (green), and avoiding cloudy regions (gray), sections close to the backscattering region, water bodies (blue), and pixels for which the input data were not usable (yellow) or retrieval algorithm failures (magenta). The red square selected region in Fig. 4a is shown in detail in the other zoomed-in maps. The fire temperature data in Fig. 4b reveal pixels that are below 500 K, which may have larger associated FRP retrieval errors (Sect. 1.1), and thus should be analyzed carefully. The fire area shown in Fig. 4c helps understand the fraction of sub-pixels corresponding to the actual area under fire. Since the nominal product resolution is 4 km², assessing how much of each pixel's area is actually on fire is an important tool to mitigate burnt area overestimation. Fig. 4d shows the FRP assessed for the region, where it is possible to identify infrared emission levels above 500 MW, and smoldering areas with low FRP. Some relatively hot fire pixels ($T > 800$ K) are associated with low fire areas ($A < 50 \times 10^3$ m²) and moderate FRP ~ 300 MW. It is also possible to identify at least one hot core cluster, with elevated temperatures, fire area, and FRP. Noticeably, there are pixels with associated FRP retrievals in Fig. 4d to which no burnt area or fire temperature data was assigned in Figs. 4b and 4c. These cases need to be further investigated, and possibly filtered out of the analyses. The black square in Fig. 4d identifies a cluster subsection selected for analysis, as discussed next.

Figure 5 shows an example of a 24h FRP time series for the selected fire cluster in Fig. 4d. The series runs from August 15th to the 16th in 2020, starting at 05:00 UTC. Some nighttime retrievals are below the 34.5 MW reliability limit indicated by Li et al. (2020), hence the number of identified wildfires may be underestimated for these cases. The FRP starts to increase significantly after daybreak at 06:00 LT (Julian day coordinate 228.40 UTC in Fig. 5). The number of identified fire pixels lags behind the FRP surge for about 2h, then sees a significant, nearly exponential increase between about 8:00 and 12:00 LT. The cluster as a whole peaks with an average 72.4 fire spots, at about 330 MW FRP. This emission level was sustained for about 90 minutes, between 13:00 to 14:30 LT, which corresponds to about 1.78×10^{12} J of emitted radiant energy during this time interval. After Julian date 228.80 UTC (15:10 LT) the number of fire spots decreases steadily, reaching a minimum by 20:00 LT. At the end of the time series, the observed

⁶ <https://www.class.noaa.gov/> accessed 2021-12-01 15:00 UTC.

nighttime FRP for 1-7 remaining fire spots is highly variable in time, at an average level much higher than the previous night.

Figure 4. Example showing GOES-16 ABI retrieved active wildfire pixels in South America on August 15th, 2020 15:00 UTC. (a) Data Quality Flag identification of active fires, fire-free land surfaces, clouds, water bodies, and algorithm failures. The red square corresponds approximately to the region shown in b) to d); (b) fire temperature in K; (c) fire area in m²; (d) FRP in MW. The black box indicates a fire cluster selected for analysis, as shown in Fig. 5.

One of the challenges in this project is to account for commission and omission errors. In principle, these cannot be fully circumvented even for large clusters, such as in the case example in Fig. 5. But scrutinizing time series for selected case studies can help detect such errors. However, this process is time-consuming and prone to human judgment errors. A possible solution is to develop an analytical algorithm that tracks variations across a study area, for instance, signaling when some smaller area fire pixels in the cluster cease to be counted, or when growing fire clusters show new pixels previously undetected.

Figure 5. Example of a 24h FRP time series, from August 15th 05:00 UTC to August 16th 05:00 UTC 2020. The retrieved GOES-16 FRP for the black box in Fig. 4 is shown at 10 min intervals (red). The number of fire spots N is also indicated (blue). The dashed line indicates the 34.5 MW limit of reliable FRP retrievals according to Li et al. (2020).

The determination of spatial boundaries to discriminate between individual wildfire clusters may be subject to considerable uncertainty. Thus, objective criteria need to be established for this task. Similarly, temporal boundaries may also manifest a complex behavior, since large fires can last for several days, and may have expanding/varying spatial scales.

Considering the fixed sensor point of view in relation to the surface, and the vast region encompassed by the Amazon Basin, it is important to investigate whether retrieval biases can be related to the sensor view zenith angle. Surface pixels for which the sensor is viewed at slant angles will have a longer optical path available for gaseous absorption and emission of radiation. Therefore, distributions of temperature and FRP should be analyzed according to view zenith angle bins.

Precipitation events and the vertical distribution of water vapor in or above smoke plumes may also interfere in the time series analyses for the retrieved temperature and FRP. Although anthropic wildfires are concentrated during the dry season, the occurrence of rain episodes is not uncommon in the Amazon in that season. In principle, it would be possible to have fire events for which the waning half-life is curtailed by precipitation.

As shown by Li et al. (2020) the GOES-16 fire product is unable to detect fires smaller than a certain FRP level (Fig. 3). Therefore, gas and particulate matter emissions estimated directly from GOES-16 data will necessarily have a certain degree of underestimation if compared to higher spatial resolution data. This should be considered when contrasting this project's results to other sources.

Finally, regarding emission comparisons with estimates derived by other remote sensing instruments, it is important to indicate this can be a challenging task. Spatial and temporal collocation of two

datasets needs to address measuring limitations that affect both instruments, including for instance the occurrence of clouds in the line of sight, the view zenith angle in each case, definition of a representative spatial domain for the particular variable, among others. At the same time, enough statistics in instrument matchups are needed to derive meaningful comparisons. Although this is a very important step, it can also be a time-consuming effort.

4. Timetable

This project is intended to take place for 36 months, according to the following schedule.

Activity	Semester					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Course credits	X	X	X			
Language exam	X					
Delimiting regions of interest in the Amazon		X				
Wildfire characterization by vegetation type		X	X	X	X	
Correlation with inventories			X	X	X	
Statistical analyses, critical comparisons				X	X	X
Publication					X	X
Dissertation writing					X	X
Master's defense						X

Open Access. This project plan is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License, which permits use, sharing, adaptation, distribution, and reproduction in any medium or format, as long as you give appropriate credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if changes were made. The images or other third-party material in this plan are included in the plan's Creative Commons license unless indicated otherwise in a credit line to the material. If material is not included in the plan's Creative Commons license and your intended use is not permitted by statutory regulation or exceeds the permitted use, you will need to obtain permission directly from the copyright holder. To view a copy of this license, visit <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

Thiago F. Nobrega

Alexandre L. Correia

References

- Brando, P.M., Soares-Filho, B., Rodrigues, L., Assunção, A., Morton, D., Tuschneider, D., Fernandes, E.C.M., Macedo, M.N., Oliveira, U., Coe, M.T., 2020. The gathering firestorm in southern Amazonia. *Sci. Adv.* 6, eaay1632. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.aay1632>
- Correia, A.L., Sena, E.T., Silva Dias, M.A.F., Koren, I., 2021. Preconditioning, aerosols, and radiation control the temperature of glaciation in Amazonian clouds. *Commun. Earth Environ.* 2, 168. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-021-00250-3>
- de Oliveira Alves, N., Vessoni, A.T., Quinet, A., Fortunato, R.S., Kajitani, G.S., Peixoto, M.S., Hacon, S. de S., Artaxo, P., Saldiva, P., Menck, C.F.M., Batistuzzo de Medeiros, S.R., 2017. Biomass burning in the Amazon region causes DNA damage and cell death in human lung cells. *Sci. Rep.* 7, 10937.

- <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-11024-3>
- He, Q., Wang, M., Yim, S.H.L., 2021. The spatiotemporal relationship between PM2.5 and AOD in China: Influencing factors and Implications for satellite PM2.5 estimations by MAIAC AOD (preprint). <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-2021-143>
- Holben, B.N., Eck, T.F., Slutsker, I., Tanré, D., Buis, J.P., Setzer, A., Vermote, E., Reagan, J.A., Kaufman, Y.J., Nakajima, T., Lavenu, F., Jankowiak, I., Smirnov, A., 1998. AERONET—A Federated Instrument Network and Data Archive for Aerosol Characterization. *Remote Sens. Environ.* 66, 1–16. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0034-4257\(98\)00031-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0034-4257(98)00031-5)
- Li, F., Zhang, X., Kondragunta, S., Schmidt, C.C., Holmes, C.D., 2020. A preliminary evaluation of GOES-16 active fire product using Landsat-8 and VIIRS active fire data, and ground-based prescribed fire records. *Remote Sens. Environ.* 237, 111600. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2019.111600>
- Libonati, R., DaCamara, C.C., Peres, L.F., Sander de Carvalho, L.A., Garcia, L.C., 2020. Rescue Brazil's burning Pantanal wetlands. *Nature* 588, 217–219. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-020-03464-1>
- Lovejoy, T.E., Nobre, C., 2019. Amazon tipping point: Last chance for action. *Sci. Adv.* 5, eaba2949. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.aba2949>
- Martins, V.S., Novo, E.M.L.M., Lyapustin, A., Aragão, L.E.O.C., Freitas, S.R., Barbosa, C.C.F., 2018. Seasonal and interannual assessment of cloud cover and atmospheric constituents across the Amazon (2000–2015): Insights for remote sensing and climate analysis. *ISPRS J. Photogramm. Remote Sens.* 145, 309–327. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2018.05.013>
- Nepstad, D., Soares-Filho, B.S., Merry, F., Lima, A., Moutinho, P., Carter, J., Bowman, M., Cattaneo, A., Rodrigues, H., Schwartzman, S., McGrath, D.G., Stickler, C.M., Lubowski, R., Piris-Cabezas, P., Rivero, S., Alencar, A., Almeida, O., Stella, O., 2009. The End of Deforestation in the Brazilian Amazon. *Science* 326, 1350–1351. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1182108>
- Pivello, V.R., Vieira, I., Christianini, A.V., Ribeiro, D.B., da Silva Menezes, L., Berlinck, C.N., Melo, F.P.L., Marengo, J.A., Tornquist, C.G., Tomas, W.M., Overbeck, G.E., 2021. Understanding Brazil's catastrophic fires: Causes, consequences and policy needed to prevent future tragedies. *Perspect. Ecol. Conserv.* 19, 233–255. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pecon.2021.06.005>
- Roberts, G., Wooster, M.J., Perry, G.L.W., Drake, N., Rebelo, L.-M., Dipotso, F., 2005. Retrieval of biomass combustion rates and totals from fire radiative power observations: Application to southern Africa using geostationary SEVIRI imagery. *J. Geophys. Res.* 110, D21111. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2005JD006018>
- Schmit, T.J., Lindstrom, S.S., Gerth, J.J., Gunshor, M.M., 2018. Applications of the 16 spectral bands on the Advanced Baseline Imager (ABI). *J. Oper. Meteorol.* 06, 33–46. <https://doi.org/10.15191/nwajom.2018.0604>
- Strand, J., Soares-Filho, B., Costa, M.H., Oliveira, U., Ribeiro, S.C., Pires, G.F., Oliveira, A., Rajão, R., May, P., van der Hoff, R., Siikamäki, J., da Motta, R.S., Toman, M., 2018. Spatially explicit valuation of the Brazilian Amazon Forest's Ecosystem Services. *Nat. Sustain.* 1, 657–664. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-018-0175-0>
- Ten Hove, J.E., Remer, L.A., Correia, A.L., Jacobson, M.Z., 2012. Recent shift from forest to savanna burning in the Amazon Basin observed by satellite. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 7, 024020. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/7/2/024020>
- Wooster, M., Zhukov, B., Oertel, D., 2003. Fire radiative energy for quantitative study of biomass burning: derivation from the BIRD experimental satellite and comparison to MODIS fire products. *Remote Sens. Environ.* 86, 83–107. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0034-4257\(03\)00070-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0034-4257(03)00070-1)
- Wooster, M.J., Roberts, G., Perry, G.L.W., Kaufman, Y.J., 2005. Retrieval of biomass combustion rates and totals from fire radiative power observations: FRP derivation and calibration relationships between biomass consumption and fire radiative energy release. *J. Geophys. Res.* 110, D24311. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2005JD006318>
- Wooster, M.J., Roberts, G.J., Giglio, L., Roy, D.P., Freeborn, P.H., Boschetti, L., Justice, C., Ichoku, C., Schroeder, W., Davies, D., Smith, A.M.S., Setzer, A., Csiszar, I., Strydom, T., Frost, P., Zhang, T., Xu, W., de Jong, M.C., Johnston, J.M., Ellison, L., Vadrevu, K., Sparks, A.M., Nguyen, H., McCarty, J., Tanpipat, V., Schmidt, C., San-Miguel-Ayanz, J., 2021. Satellite remote sensing of active fires: History and current status, applications and future requirements. *Remote Sens. Environ.* 267, 112694. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2021.112694>
- Xu, W., Wooster, M.J., He, J., Zhang, T., 2021. Improvements in high-temporal resolution active fire detection and FRP retrieval over the Americas using GOES-16 ABI with the geostationary Fire Thermal Anomaly (FTA) algorithm. *Sci. Remote Sens.* 3, 100016. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.srs.2021.100016>